

Study on Physicochemical Properties of Sufu during Post-fermentation

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Sufu is a kind of soybean fermented food. In this experiment, the physical and chemical properties of seven commercial sufu and two kinds of self-made sufu were determined, and the changes of physicochemical indexes during post-fermentation were detected. The results showed that the physicochemical properties of the seven commercial sufu all meet the standard, while the total acid content of the two self-made sufu is not in line with the standard. Through the analysis of the physical and chemical indexes of two kinds of self-made fermented bean curd in different post fermentation periods, it was found that the content of amino acid nitrogen was positively correlated with the post fermentation time, while the content of water-soluble protein was negatively correlated with the post fermentation time.

Keywords: SUFU; YELLOW RICE WINE; CAMELLIA OIL

Introduction

Sufu, also known as fermented bean curd, is a traditional Chinese fermented soybean food with a history of more than 1500 years in China (DW, et al., 2019). It is similar to cheese in processing technology and ripening mechanism and is called “Chinese cheese” in Europe and America (Zhang, et al., 2021). As an appetizer or a side dish (YC, et al., 2019; X, et al., 2019), it is deeply loved by Chinese and some other Asian consumers because of its good taste and high nutrition.

Sufu is a secondary bean product made from soybean by microbial fermentation. Soybean is a traditional agricultural crop in China, cheap and easy to obtain. It contains not only a large amount of protein but also soybean isoflavones (Kim, et al., 2005), soybean lecithin (Han, 2003), and unsaturated fatty acids. However, there are some problems to prevent soybean protein from an effective use, such as hard grain tissue, harmful substances, fishy smell, and low utilization rate. In the production process of sufu, the raw material of soybean

has almost no loss of nutrition. Instead, it produces a variety of delicious and fragrant alcohols, esters, organic acids, and amino acids (Liu, et al., 2018), which makes sufu more nutritious than soybean.

The fermentation process of sufu is mainly divided into pre-fermentation and post-fermentation stages (Liang, et al., 2019). In the pre-fermentation process, it is mainly the growth and development of *Mucor*, *Rhizopus*, yeast, *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Monascus*, and a few bacteria, which form hyphae around the tofu and secretes various enzymes, resulting in the saccharification of a small amount of starch and the gradual degradation of protein in tofu. In the post-fermentation stage, it is mainly carried out after adding different auxiliary materials such as salt, camellia oil, or yellow rice wine, and a variety of microorganisms and enzymes cooperate to participate in the biochemical reaction process. After complex biochemical changes, the protein is decomposed into peptones, peptides, and amino acids, and some organic acids, alcohols, esters, and amino acids are generated at the same time. The special color, aroma, and taste of fermented bean curd are mainly formed at this stage. However, due to the traditional development production mode, Sufu is very easy to be contaminated by miscellaneous bacteria, resulting in potential safety hazards. Therefore, the quality and safety control in the post-fermentation process of sufu production is a hot issue in the sufu industry. So, it is critical to detect the quality of sufu during post-fermentation.

In this research, the differences of seven kinds of commercial sufu and two kinds of self-made sufu were compared by measuring the physical and chemical indexes of these samples. Furthermore, the physicochemical properties of the two kinds of sufu made in the laboratory during post-fermentation were detected. We hope our research could provide a useful reference for improving the quality of sufu.

Materials and methods

1.1 Sufu Samples

1.1.1 Commercial Sufu Samples

Seven distinctive types of commercial sufu (N1-N7) were produced around the same season and directly purchased from five different manufacturers located in Hengyang City, Hunan Province, China. All the sufu samples were placed at room temperature.

1.1.2 Sufu made in the laboratory

Sufu pehtze were collected randomly from a company in Hengyang City, Hunan Province, China. Before being collected, these pehtze were placed in a room with an appropriate humidity of 90-95% and a constant temperature of 18°C for almost 3-4 d so they could use the molds contained in the air to perform natural fermentation. Next, these sufu pehtze were cut into cubes with the size of approximately 2×2×1 cm. Meanwhile, salt, chili powder, and five-spice powder were added to the mixing basin and mixed well with a spoon. Then, these sufu cubes were wrapped with the dressing mixture and arranged into the sterilized bottles, and stored at room temperature for 24 h. After that yellow rice wine (S1) or camellia oil (S2) was poured into the bottles up to submerge the sufu cube surface for 2 cm. Finally, the bottles were covered and sealed and placed at room temperature (approximately 25°C) for almost another 40 days for post-fermentation. During the ripening period

on days 0, 7, 14, 21, 28, and 35, three bottles were drawn arbitrarily. Samples from each stage were randomly selected in triplicates, which were then ground, mixed, and pooled into sterile bags to provide an experimental sufu mashed sample (approximately 100 g). Three distinct batches of sufu samples were collected for adequate representation.

1.2 Pretreatment of Samples

Sample preparation: take out the sample from the storage bottle and stand for almost 30 minutes to remove the soup and other impurities. Take about 150 g of sufu sample without the soup and impurities, grind it to paste, and mix it well for standby.

Preparation of sample solution: weigh about 20 g of sufu sample into a 150 mL beaker, boil it with water, remove it, cool it to room temperature, then move it into a 250 mL volumetric flask, add water to the scale, mix it evenly, filter it into a grinding flask with dry filter paper and keep it for standby.

1.3 Determination of water content (Zhou Ying, 2010)

Sample pretreatment: weigh 5-10 g of each sample from the sample fermented bean curd, put it on the funnel, and stand for 30 min to remove the soup.

Place a weighing bottle into a 105°C drying oven to dry for 4 h, take it out for cooling, weigh it with constant weight, weigh 5.00 g of sample in a known constant temperature weighing bottle, accurately weigh it, place the loaded bottle in a drying chamber, removing the lid and leaving it also in the chamber. Dry the test specimen at the temperature of 100-105°C for 4 h. Upon opening the chamber, close the bottle promptly, and take it out. Put the bottle into a desiccator for drying for 0.5 h before weigh it, and repeat the above operation. Until the mass difference between the two times is no more than 2 mg, it is regarded as the constant weight.

1.4 Determination of salt content (Jiang Liting, 2012)

Take the above test solution into a 150 mL conical flask, add 50 mL of water and 1 mL of potassium complex indicator, and mix well. Titrate with silver nitrate standard titration solution (0.100 mol / L) until it initially shows brick red and does not change color for half a minute, then the titration endpoint is reached. Record the volume of silver nitrate standard titration solution consumed. At the same time, conduct a reagent blank test, and record the volume of silver nitrate standard titration solution consumed.

1.5 Determination of total acid content (Halle Hassi buick, 2015)

Take 10 mL of the above sample filtrate, place it in a 150 mL beaker, add 50 mL of water, turn on the magnetic stirrer, and titrate it with 0.05 mol / L NaOH solution to pH 8.2. Record the volume of sodium hydroxide standard solution consumed at 0.05 mol / L. Blank measurements are carried out under the same experimental conditions.

1.6 Determination of amino acid nitrogen

Take 10 ml of sample filtrate, put it into a 150 ml beaker, add 50 ml of water, turn on the magnetic stirrer, and titrate it with 0.10 mol / L NaOH solution to pH = 8.2. Add 10 ml formaldehyde, titrate to pH = 9.2, record the consumed volume, and blank control experiment are carried out under the same conditions.

1.7 Determination of water-soluble protein content

Weigh 2 g of sufu sample, accurate to 0.001 g, into the digestion tube, and then add 0.4 g CuSO₄, 6 g K₂SO₄ and 20 ml H₂SO₄ to the digestion furnace for digestion. When the temperature of the digestion furnace reaches 420°C, continue digestion for 1 h. At this time, the liquid in the digestion tube is green and transparent. Take it out and add 50 ml water after cooling. The process of automatic liquid addition, distillation, titration and recording titration data is performed on the Automatic Kjeldahl nitrogen determiner.

1.8 Statistical Analysis

The experiments have been performed in triplicates. Student's t-test was used to analyze the differences between control and test, whereas ANOVA determined the differences in the various assays. Differences with p values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant. IBM SPSS Statistics 24.0 software was used for statistical data analysis.

Results and Analysis

2.1 Analysis of physicochemical index of sufu

According to SB / T 10170-2007, the domestic trade industry standard of the people's Republic of China — fermented bean curd, the physical and chemical indexes of red fermented bean curd should meet the following requirements: water content ≤ 75.0%; amino acid nitrogen (calculated as nitrogen) ≥ 0.35 g / 100 g; water-soluble protein ≥ 3.20 g / 100 g; total acid (calculated by lactic acid) ≤ 1.30 g / 100 g; salt (calculated by sodium chloride) ≥ 6.5g / 100 g.

Table1 Analysis of physicochemical index of sufu

Samples	Water (%)	total acid content (g/100 g)	amino acid nitrogen (g/100 g)	salt content (g/100 g)	water-soluble protein content (g/100 g)
N1	70.02±0.11	0.78±0.04	0.53±0.06	8.65±0.04	6.23±0.11
N2	68.56±0.05	0.65±0.05	0.47±0.05	8.32±0.05	5.38±0.08
N3	64.75±0.15	0.84±0.08	0.60±0.03	7.48±0.08	6.84±0.07
N4	66.97±0.13	0.82±0.05	0.58±0.04	9.56±0.12	6.47±0.12
N5	65.87±0.20	0.79±0.09	0.46±0.05	10.27±0.07	8.29±0.10
N6	67.66±0.08	0.87±0.10	0.58±0.06	9.12±0.05	7.48±0.07
N7	66.83±0.16	0.64±0.04	0.72±0.05	7.25±0.07	7.05±0.08
S1	64.04±0.15	2.18±0.03	0.80±0.10	7.35±0.06	7.39±0.05
S2	40.00±0.10	2.54±0.05	0.85±0.08	7.48±0.08	7.85±0.06

It can be seen from Table 1 that the water content, amino acid nitrogen, water-soluble protein, and salt content of the seven kinds of commercial sufu N1-N7 all meet the requirements, but the total acid content of the two self-made sufu is higher than 2.00 g / 100 g, which are not in line with the standard. That may be related to the hydrolysis and oxidation of lipids, and may also be related to the microbial flora in the post-fermentation period.

2.2 Changes of amino acid nitrogen content in Sufu during post-fermentation

The length of post ripening time has a great impact on the taste and nutritional components of sufu. With the extension of post ripening time, the content of amino acids shows an upward trend. However, if the post

ripening time is too long, the content of amino acid nitrogen shows a slow-growth trend. In the figure above, S1 represents the sample of sufu added with yellow rice wine, and S2 represents the sample of sufu added with camellia oil.

Fig. 1 Changes of amino acid nitrogen content during the post-fermentation

As can be seen from Fig. 1, the content of amino acid nitrogen in different sufu samples increased with the extension of days. The content of amino acid nitrogen increased greatly in the first 14 days during the post-fermentation process of sufu because the production of various enzymes and protein decomposition was promoted at the presence of various microorganisms, thus making the content of amino acid nitrogen in sufu increased rapidly. During the subsequent 20 days of fermentation, it may be due to the effect of salt, wine, and oil permeating into sufu, which will affect the activities of various enzymes resulting in the amino acid nitrogen increased at a lower rate. By comparison, the content of amino acid nitrogen in S2 added with camellia oil is higher than that in S1 added with yellow rice wine. The reason may be that the inhibition effect on various enzymes in S2 is smaller than S1, so the content of amino acid nitrogen in S2 is relatively higher.

2.3 Changes of water content in Sufu during post-fermentation

Fig. 2 Changes of amino acid nitrogen content during the post-fermentation

the changes of water content of the both self-made sufu tends to increase slightly during post-fermentation. The water content of S2 is significantly lower than that of S1 and the seven kinds of commercial sufu. The reason is that S2 is added with camellia oil, which is insoluble in water.

2.4 Changes of salt content in Sufu during post-fermentation

Salt is not only used for seasoning, but also for bacteriostasis, anti-corrosion and deterioration. The

appropriate salt concentration also affects the role of protease in fermentation. It can be seen from Table 2 that the salt content of sufu does not change greatly during post-fermentation.

Table 2 Changes of salt content during post-fermentation

fermentation time (d)	S1 (g/100 g)	S2 (g/100g)
1	8.6	8.1
7	8.4	7.6
14	6.9	7.0
21	7.1	6.4
28	6.7	6.9
35	7.4	7.5

2.5 Changes of total acid content in Sufu during post-fermentation

Table 3 Changes of total acid during post-fermentation

fermentation time (d)	S1 (g/100 g)	S2 (g/100g)
1	1.60	1.13
7	1.15	1.89
14	2.50	2.61
21	2.20	2.78
28	2.73	2.81
35	2.70	2.95

The total acidity of the two sufu samples increases with the gradual progress of post ripening, due to the production of acid by microorganisms in the post-fermentation process. In the study on the physical and chemical properties of different types of fermented bean curd by Ma (Ma Yanli, et al., 2015), it was found that the total acid content of white sufu, green sufu, red sufu, and Qingfang sufu was about 1.66 g / 100 g, 0.81 g / 100 g, 1.23 g / 100 g, and 1.21 g /100 g, respectively. The total acid content of Qingfang fermented bean curd is lower than that of other types of fermented bean curd, which may be related to the high content of ammonia and other basic compounds in Qingfang fermented bean curd. In this study, the total acid content of sample S2 added with camellia oil is the highest in the 35 days of fermentation, reaching 2.95 g / 100 g. It is preliminarily considered that the added camellia oil has isolation effect, which makes the fermentation environment anoxic, and microbial metabolism produces lactic acid, which increases the total acid content.

2.6 Changes of water-soluble protein content in Sufu during post-fermentation

With the increase of fermentation time, the content of water-soluble protein in fermented bean curd decreased gradually. Under the action of microorganism, protein hydrolyzed and amino acid content increased.

Fig. 3 Changes of water-soluble protein content during post-fermentation

Conclusion

The physical and chemical indexes of 7 kinds of sufu were detected and found to meet the requirements of the standard of SB / T 10170-2007. The content of amino acid nitrogen in fermented bean curd increased with the extension of post-fermentation time, while the content of water-soluble protein decreased with the extension of post-fermentation time. This is mainly because the protein in fermented bean curd is degraded under the action of microorganisms and enzymes to produce amino acids.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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